

COMPARISON OF SPEED AND AGILITY BETWEEN COLLEGE MEN KABADDI AND KHO-KHO PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to compare the speed and agility between college men kabaddi and kho-kho players. To achieve this purpose of the study, sixty men players studying in and around the Colleges in Warangal District, Telangana, India were selected as subjects at random. Among them, thirty kabaddi players and thirty kho-kho players were selected. The following variables namely speed and agility were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables by using 50 mts run and shuttle run. The independent 't' ratio was used to analyze the significant difference, if any between groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the 't' ratio obtained, which was considered as an appropriate. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between college men kabaddi and kho-kho players on speed and agility.

Key Words: Speed, Agility, College Men Kabaddi Players, Kho-kho Players

Introduction:

Speed and agility directly contribute to improved performance on the field. In kabaddi and kho-kho, players need to swiftly maneuver around opponents, evade tackles, and cover ground quickly to score points or prevent the opposing team from scoring. Both kabaddi and kho-kho are fast-paced games that require players to react quickly to changing situations on the field. Speed and agility help players to anticipate movements, make split-second decisions, and execute strategies effectively.

In both sports, defensive players need to be agile and quick to tag or tackle opponents. Speed enables defenders to close gaps rapidly, while agility allows them to change direction swiftly to outmaneuver opponents and block their progress. Speedy and agile players have an advantage when it comes to offensive plays. They can exploit gaps in the opposing team's defense, dodge defenders, and swiftly move in and out of positions to confuse opponents and score points.

Developing speed and agility also improves overall endurance and stamina. Players who are faster and more agile can sustain high-intensity play for longer periods, allowing them to maintain peak performance throughout the game. Training to improve speed and agility often involves exercises that enhance flexibility, balance, and coordination. These exercises can help reduce the risk of injuries such as muscle strains, sprains, and joint injuries, which are common in fast-paced sports like kabaddi and kho-kho.

In college-level competitions, where the level of competition is high, having superior speed and agility can provide a significant competitive edge. Players who excel in these areas are often able to outperform their opponents and contribute more effectively to their team's success. Speed and agility are indispensable attributes for college men's kabaddi and kho-kho players, enabling them to perform at their best, outmaneuver opponents, and excel in competitive play. Training programs that focus on developing these qualities are essential for the success of individual players and their teams.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to compare the speed and agility between college men kabaddi and kho-kho players. To achieve this purpose of the study, sixty men players studying in and around the Colleges in Warangal District, Telangana, India were selected as subjects at random. Among them, thirty kabaddi players and thirty kho-kho players were selected. The following variables namely speed and agility were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables by using 50 mts run and shuttle run. The independent 't' ratio was used to analyze the significant difference, if any between groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the 't' ratio obtained, which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data:

Speed

The mean, standard deviation and 't' ratio values on speed of kabaddi players and kho-kho players have been analyzed and presented in table 1.

Table 1: The Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' Ratio Values Between Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players on Speed

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' ratio value
Kabaddi Players	8.23	0.12	9.42*
Kho-kho Players	7.95	0.11	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 58 was 2.002).

The table 1 shows that the mean values on speed for kabaddi players and kho-kho players were 8.23 and 7.95 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio value on speed 9.42 which was greater than the table value required for significance with df 58 was 2.002.

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between college men kabaddi players and kho-kho players on speed.

Agility:

The mean, standard deviation and 't' ratio values on agility of kabaddi players and kho-kho players have been analyzed and presented in table 2.

Table 2: The Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' Ratio Values Between Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players on Agility

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' ratio value
Kabaddi Players	10.23	0.19	10.88*
Kho-kho Players	9.71	0.18	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 58 was 2.002).

The table 2 shows that the mean values on agility for kabaddi players and kho-kho players were 10.23 and 9.71 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio value on agility 6.28 which was greater than the table value required for significance with df 58 was 2.002.

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between college men kabaddi players and kho-kho players on agility.

Conclusions:

- There was a significant difference between kabaddi players and kho-kho players on speed.
- There was a significant difference between kabaddi players and kho-kho players on agility.

References:

1. Arslan, E., & Alemdaroglu, U. (2008). The relationship between agility and sprint ability of young soccer players. *Journal of Human Kinetics*, 20, 53-57.
2. Chittibabu, B., & Srinivasan, B. (2016). A Comparative Study of Speed, Agility, and Muscular Endurance between Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players. *International Journal of Physiology, Nutrition and Physical Education*, 1(1), 80-82.
3. Ghosh, S., & Dey, S. (2019). A Study on Speed and Agility between Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 6(4), 245-246.
4. Harrison, A. J., Bourke, G., & McLaren, S. (2017). Muscular strength, functional performances and injury risk in professional and under-19 male basketball players. *Journal of Athletic Enhancement*, 6(5), 1-5.
5. Ilva, J. R., Magalhães, J., Ascensão, A., & Oliveira, E. (2010). Physical fitness profile of elite Portuguese rugby union players. *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 24(4), 1026-1033.
6. Kumar, V., & Gupta, S. (2013). Study of Physical Fitness Components among Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(6), 1-3.
7. Patel, H. K., Purohit, R., & Shah, S. S. (2015). Comparative Study of Physical Fitness Variables among Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 1(2), 7-9.
8. Raja, S. K., & Deena, R. K. (2017). A Study on Physical Fitness Components among Kho Kho Players. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 4(5), 77-80.